

Toxicological Studies of Unused Paracetamol and Its Biodegradation

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Abstract:

After COVID usage of analgesic and antipyretic drug has increased many folds. For that, the occurrence of pharmaceutical products (PhPs) has increased in recent time. Flushing drugs into the sewage system are still a common practice in developed country also. Only very few countries follow the practice of returning drugs to pharmacy in a larger extent. Due to improper disposal method a large number of pharmaceutically active compounds (PhACs) have been inflowing into the environment from the industry as well as individual human activity in soil and the marine environment worldwide. Paracetamol is easily dissolved and absorbed or accumulated in aquatic organisms. It directly or indirectly affects the life cycle of other inhabitants of the ecology. The impact of paracetamol on the environment is enormous, and if degradation of this is not done, the occurrence of these compounds will have a negative impact on the environment, communities, and wildlife. Such pollutants account for the global increase in the incidence of cancer, cardiovascular diseases, genetic disorders and Multiple Drug Resistance (MDR). As the PhACs usage has amplified, the quantity of PhACs into the water body has also increased which may show an adverse effect in the environment. Therefore, significant attention should be engrossed on the detection and decontamination of PhACs on the marine system. Our objective is to develop a simple microbial-based technique for degradation of paracetamol (N-acetyl-4-amino-phenol). Paracetamol is a popular antipyretic and analgesic medication with market size of US\$126.1 million in 2022. Over the last few years, presence of paracetamol is observed into the aquatic environment and soil of 0.101–20.86 µg/L from the manufacturing industry/through individual human activity. Selection of microbes capable of degrading pharmaceutical waste products are done from the waste water collected from waterbody near to the hospital in Haldia. Four different types of bacteria are selected for further experiment. Detoxification of paracetamol is checked using UV–vis spectrophotometer. Agar diffusional assay is performed to confirm the cytotoxic effect of biodegraded paracetamol.

Keywords: Paracetamol, Toxicology, Aquatic environment, Detoxification, Microbes

1. Introduction

A wide range of exclusive emerging pollutants, including pharmaceuticals and their metabolites are continuously presented into environment mostly from clinic and community wastewater, consumer use, or disposal and discharges from medicinal production^{1,3}. Paracetamol (4'-hydroxyacetanilide, N-acetyl-p-aminophenol, C₈H₉NO₂) (fig.1), is a widely used as over-the-counter analgesic and antipyretic drug.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of paracetamol

Paracetamol is abundant in the natural environment and simply gather in aquatic environment, which have been noticed in surface waters, wastewater, and drinking water throughout the globe. Paracetamol concentration was found 0.101–20.86 µg/L in the wastewater in Kuwait. The United Kingdom more than 65 µg/L in Tyne River and drinking water contain 0.211 µg/L. Common occurrence of these composites in the environment and drinking water has

elevated a

concern. Paracetamol concentration can reach more than 100 µg/L in Waste Water Treatment Plant (WWTP) and more than 100 µg/L in rivers⁴⁻⁶.

Earlier studies on omission of paracetamol from effluent mainly absorbed on chemical methods which may not be desirable as it generates secondary pollutants, and the high operational cost⁷. Biodiversity in aquatic system is in threat due to micropollutants⁸. Oliveira et al. 2015, mentioned some pharmaceuticals, which may assist their undesirable impact on biotic community low biodegradability, bioaccumulation, pseudo-persistence, since the rate of these chemicals removal is waged by the regular input of new particles into the environment⁹⁻¹⁰.

After COVID, production of analgesic and antipyretic drug has increased many folds. These are intended as biologically active molecules, which should be effective in diverse group of species¹¹⁻¹³. Parolini and Binelli 2012 cautioned that high activity of pharmaceuticals can impress the health status of the biotic community.

Thus, environmental risk can be calculated on the basis of eco-toxicological data accessible for particular medicine¹⁴⁻¹⁵. In this contribution paracetamol was degraded predominantly using the bacteria isolated from hospital wastewater.

2. Material and methods

2.1 Sample collection

Hospital effluent were collected from the four different spot which are in rich source of unused paracetamol products at Haldia subdivision. Spot-1 Haldia sub-Divisional Hospital, Spot-2 Baraghasipur BPHC Community Health Center, Spot-3 Haldia institute of Health Science (HIHS), Spot-4 Chaitanyapur Bus stand areas which are enormously visited for medical purpose. The effluent was used as a source of paracetamol degrading bacteria. Samples were collected in 25ml falcon tube covered with brown paper during April to June. Normal pond water was also collected as a source of natural aquatic microbes in a 25ml falcon tube covered with brown paper.

2.2. Preparation of stock solution of paracetamol

Paracetamol tablets were purchased from local shop. Two tablets of Paracetamol having Paracetamol content 400 mg each was crushed with mortar pestle and dissolved in methanol (20ml) and kept for stirring for 2 h. Then sample was filtered using blotting paper. Filtrate was air dried to make it powder. Dried paracetamol of 10mg was dissolved with 700 µl of DMSO and then volume is filled up to 1000 µl with distilled water.

2.3. Isolation of paracetamol degrading bacteria

Each water sample was incubated (10 µl) with LB medium (500 µl) and was kept overnight at 37 °C. After incubation 10 µl of each sample (1- 4 set) was spreaded on LB agar plate. Single colony was isolated and used for further experiment.

2.4. Toxicological studies of paracetamol and its detoxification

Toxicological study was executed on natural aquatic microbes, collected from freshwater. Water sample was spreaded on LB agar medium and five pits are made. Different concentration of paracetamol (0.087264mg/ml, 0.1818mg/ml, 0.2734mg/ml, 0.3636mg/ml) and solvent (7: 3 DMSO: water) were given in the well and incubated at 37° C nightlong to check the toxicity.

Detoxification of paracetamol was studied with bacteria isolated from hospital effluent. 0.3636 mg/ml paracetamol was treated with bacteria in Sugarcane Bagasse media for

overnight at 37°C. After the treatment sample was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes. 100 µl of both bacteria treated and untreated sample was put in a well of LB agar plate coated with aquatic microbes. Plates were incubated at 37°C overnight. After the incubation period, clear zones were measured around the well.

Calculation of Detoxification percentage was used the following equation:

Detoxification (%) = $\frac{Z_c - Z_t}{Z_c} \times 100$ [Where, Z_c = the zone of inhibition of control (paracetamol in water) Z_t = the zone of inhibition of treated sample separately].

2.5. Detoxification procedure of paracetamol

Detoxification of paracetamol is done by either degradation or absorption. For absorption, paracetamol was absorbed on cell surface which will be identified by studying the UV-Vis spectra where peak values decrease. For biotransformation new peak should be generated. To study the mode of paracetamol removal, all samples were centrifuged and supernatant was collected and scanned range 200-800nm using Genesys 10S UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Isolation of paracetamol degrading bacteria from hospital effluent

Various types (morphological) of colonies were observed in a LB agar plate which having normal pond water whereas only four types of colonies were observed which having hospital effluent (Fig. 1). This indicates that biodiversity is rich in normal water. Due to pharmaceutical waste some particular type of bacteria is able to grow in hospital effluent. Four bacterial colonies were further incubated with 0.3636 mg/ml of paracetamol and colonies were observed. The four distinct colonies were selected and named as Paracetamol Degrading Bacteria (PDB) PDB I, PDB II, PDB III, PDB IV.

Fig.2. Bacterial colony from Healthy Pond (i) and Hospital effluent (ii)

3.2. Toxicological studies of paracetamol

After the incubation period of aquatic microbes with different concentration of paracetamol, clear zones were observed (Fig. 3). With increasing concentration clear zone around the well increases due to the cytotoxic effect of paracetamol. Clear zones were measured and toxicity was calculated¹⁶.

Fig. 3. Concentration dependent toxicity test. (i) 0.087264 mg/ml (ii) 0.1818 mg/ml (iii) 0.2734 mg/ml (iv) 0.3636 mg/ml Paracetamol and (vi) Solvent (DMSO: Water, 7:3).

3.3. Detoxification study of Bacteria

Fig. 4 indicates the detoxification of paracetamol. UV-Vis spectra of paracetamol in presence and absence with bacteria clearly indicate biotransformation of paracetamol. Absorbance decreases with shift. Peak at 250 nm is blue shifted (245 nm $\leftarrow$ 250 nm) and new peak is generated at 320 nm. Detoxification of paracetamol on aquatic microbes was confirmed by gel diffusional assay (Fig. 4 inset). Detoxification % of paracetamol was observed as 35 % (Table 1.)

Sample	Zone diameter around the well (mm)	Detoxification percentage
Paracetamol (Control)	2	

Fig. 4. UV-Vis spectra of paracetamol in presence and absence with bacteria. (inset) Detoxification study of paracetamol on aquatic microbes. (i) Ibuprofen (ii) Ibuprofen treated with bacteria (iii) Paracetamol (iv) Paracetamol treated with bacteria

4. Conclusion:

From the above results, we can conclude that hospital effluent having only few bacteria due to its pharmaceutically active components. Paracetamol showed cytotoxic effect on aquatic microbes. Detoxification of paracetamol can be achieved using microbes. In this contribution low cost media is also formulated with SBP for bacterial growth.

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Swati Maiti has been working as Assistant Professor at the Department of Biotechnology, Haldia Institute of Technology, Haldia, India since 2010. She received her PhD from Maulana Abul Kalam Azad University of Technology, West Bengal in Environmental Toxicology. During her PhD, she worked on the impact of hair dye and its residual discharge on the environment. She has eight international publications and three patents. She is passionate about microbial technology for the detection and bioremediation of pollutants and recycling and the reuse of waste for clean water and environmental sustainability.

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